

NANO · MICRO
small

Supporting Information

for *Small*, DOI 10.1002/smll.202500043

Electrochemical Scanning Microwave Microscopy Reveals Ion Intercalation Dynamics and Maps Active Sites in 2D Catalyst

*Mohamed Awadein, Abhishek Kumar, Yuqing Wang, Mingdong Dong, Stefan Müllegger and Georg Gramse**

Supporting Information

Electrochemical Scanning Microwave Microscopy Reveals Ion Intercalation Dynamics and Maps Active Sites in 2D Catalyst

Mohamed Awadein,[†] Abhishek Kumar,[‡] Yuqing Wang,[¶] Mingdong Dong,[¶] Stefan
Müllegger,[§] and Georg Gramse^{*,||}

[†]*Keysight Labs Austria, Keysight Technologies, Linz 4020, Austria*

[‡]*Institute of Semiconductor and Solid-State Physics, Johannes Kepler University, Linz
4040, Austria*

[¶]*Interdisciplinary Nanoscience Center (iNANO), Aarhus University, Aarhus C, DK-8000
Denmark*

[§]*Institute of Semiconductor and Solid State Physics, Johannes Kepler University, Linz
4040, Austria*

^{||}*Institute of Biophysics, Johannes Kepler University, Linz 4020, Austria*

E-mail: georg.gramse@jku.at

Supporting Note 1

S_{11} and imaginary part of C^* and images

Figure S1: Imaginary part of the acquired complex capacitance C^* and S_{11} image a-c) C'' at different potentials as indicated. d) Topography profile in comparison with C'' profiles. e-g) Images of S_{11} amplitude at different potentials. h) The profile of topography versus the profile of S_{11} .

The images of the $\omega G = C''$ channel at different potentials show similar as the images of $C = C'$, where the edge also shows enhanced electrochemical activity. The cross-talk can also be verified here by comparing the profiles. Figure S1 c) shows the images of S_{11} at a different potential. Nevertheless, there is almost no potential dependency on the S_{11} profiles. In contrast to direct S_{11} images (Fig. S1) that visualize both the geometrical capacitance of the flake together with the presence of surface charges, in dS_{11}/dV images only the charge that follows the kHz modulation voltage is measured. The cross-talk can be also verified from the HOPG step that can hardly be distinguished by the S_{11} signal.

Supporting Figures

Figure S2: Topography of a NiCo layered double hydroxides flakes in 0.1 mM KOH at different applied voltages. The size and the topographical morphology of the flake changed at different electrochemical potentials.

Figure S3: Lateral resolution of the electrochemical signal. a) Electrochemical capacitance image (size $2.5 \mu\text{m} \times 2.5 \mu\text{m}$). b) -c) Profile lines and estimation of the lateral resolution. The lateral resolution on the double-flake was estimated with $x_{10-90} = 25 \pm 1 \text{ nm}$.

Figure S4: Cyclic voltammograms acquired at the center of the flake at different frequencies.